

“Corporate Governance and Firm Financial Performance: A Conceptual Framework and Research Propositions”

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Abstract

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The intention of this conceptual paper is to evaluate the consequences of corporate governance (CG) on firm's financial performance (FFP). This paper studies the effect of corporate governance mechanism (CGM) i.e. Board size (BS), CEO duality (CD), insider Shareholder (IS), board independence (BI), audit committees (AC), board diligence (BD) and the role of women on board (RWB) on FFP via Return on Assets (ROA), Earning per share (EPS) and Tobin's Q. I've incorporated stewardship theory, agency theory and stakeholder theory and consider the leverage, industry and firm size as controllable variables. This study explored that a well-organized structured corporate governance mechanism influences the FFP positively. Increases the investor trust as well as enhances the sustained advancement along with financial strength of the firm. This study additionally explains the well-structured CG considers shareholder priorities, managers besides stakeholders. Furthermore, CGM enhances effective strategic decision making and improves risk management and oversight the managers' affairs efficiently.

Keywords: Stewardship Theory, corporate governance, Stakeholder Theory, Board composition, Firm's

financial performance, Agency Theory.

Introduction

CG has a crucial function in improving transparency, supervisory system, accountability and strategic decision making to manage the business affairs effectively and enhance the FFP. CG structure helps to oversight and manage the business efficiently and solved the agency problems effectively that's why investors interests increases and company makes long-term progress (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). In previous years, a lot of research work has been done on different aspects of CG emphasizing board structure, supervision system and stockholding administration and its effect on FFP (Fama & Jensen, 1983). This research examines the effect of corporate governance in relation to

the firm's financial performance that has been measured through various factors including BS, BI, IS, AC, CD and some other factors such as RWB and BD that were not studied earlier in this context now included in this study to explore new perspectives. For FFP measurement different indicators like Tobin's Q, ROA EPS have been chosen (Demsetz & Villalonga, 2001). For comprehensive and effective results firm size, leverage and industry has been considered controllable variables. This conceptual paper provides strong theoretical foundations because in this paper different theories like agency theory, stewardship theory and stakeholder theory have been discussed in detail. The agency theory states that to align the interests of managers with shareholders interest company should adopt effective CGM. While the Stewardship theory (Donaldson & Davis, 1991) asserts that managers prioritize the interests of shareholders, work honestly and oversight the business affairs effectively for their sustainable growth.

It also states that the role of CEO and chairperson should be held by one individual. So, that company affairs can be managed smoothly. The Stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984) provides more depth of corporate governance by highlighting that a firm should not focus only on the interests of the shareholders. An organization should consider the concerns of all individuals who are directly or indirectly linked with companies such as suppliers, employees, government etc. to make great reputation, long-term profit and sustainable growth. Moreover, sophisticated and comprehensive understanding that how a well-organized corporate mechanism affects the FFP has been examined in this conceptual paper. To cut a long story short, a brief theoretical foundation has been provided by discussing different theories such as agency theory, stakeholder theory and stewardship theory along with different dimensions of well-organized CG including different factors have been discussed in detail and their impact on FFP has been explored on basis of existing literature.

LITERATURE REVIEW

SPECIFICATION OF THEORY

Agency Theory

The concept of agency theory, suggested by Jensen and Meckling (1976), clarifies that those who financially contribute to a company are called shareholders and have ownership of business, while managers run the company and have the power (control) to make decisions regarding company. So, there can be conflicts among managers (agents) and Shareholder (principals), because Manager's can work for their own interests instead of shareholders benefits. This conflict leads to agency costs, which the company has to bear and might affect FFP negatively. To regulate corporate affairs smoothly that managers work for shareholders' interests, companies face agency cost that comprises bonding cost, monitoring expenses and residual losses. Agency costs are not good for a company, as they are reflected in firm's valuation and also demonstrate the stock market performance of the firm (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). An effective mechanism of CG, like well-structured executives and independent boards, ensures that managers' objectives are consistent with those of the shareholders, this effective mechanism plays a vital role in reducing agency problems (Allen & Gale, 2001). If there are proper check and balance on tasks that are performed by managers, Manager's salary and bonuses are align with their performance, competition in the market and prudent debt management than the value of firm increases and agency cost reduces

(Bonazzi & Islam, 2007). For maintaining proper check and balance and oversight in company affairs, CG suggests that the chairperson and CEO roles should remain independent (Gillan, 2006). In this scenario, a well-organized corporate governance model is crucial for improving FFP and reducing agency conflicts.

Stewardship theory

Agency theory argues that the role of CEO and chairperson should be separated so that they can control each other while the stewardship theory recommends that CEO and chairperson role should not be separate for effective decision-making. Stewardship Theory argues that directors prioritize the shareholders' interests instead of their own interests and make decisions for benefits of the company. This claim has been upheld by some available studies (Donaldson & Davis, 1991). In addition, it has been anticipated by stewardship theory that giving flexibility to managers inspires them and as a result they work with dedication. Scholars of this perspective argue that managers did not work only for the sake of money, they also need authority to make decisions independently for the interests of shareholders.

Additionally, stewardship theory argues that managers prioritize benefits of shareholders as they want great reputation and advancement in their career and this way the agency also reduces costs (Donaldson & Davis, 1991). Moreover, Fama and Jensen (1983) states that as compared to independent directors' managers possessed more insider information about the organization. Since managers have deep information of the organization, so it is expected that they will make the decisions effectively for the best interests of the firm. The stewardship theory recommends that a smaller number of independent directors manage the company affairs smoothly (Christensen et al., 2010; Donaldson & Davis, 1991). Furthermore, insider drivers have quick and easy access to technical and information and organization so they can accomplish the firm's goals effectively. In conclusion, agency theory and stewardship theory both say that the aim of CEO is to work for the interests of shareholders instead of using his authority for his concerns (Donaldson, 1990).

Stakeholder theory

The stakeholder theory was introduced by Freeman (1984) that claims that a firm should not be limited to shareholders' interests only, it should also consider the stakeholders' benefits while making strategic decisions for sustainable growth of the firm. Stakeholder theory claims that a firm is not related to only shareholders it also includes stakeholder means suppliers, customer, employees, Society and government that are linked with company (Donaldson & Preston, 1995). This theory highlights that a firm should not only focus on shareholders' interests it should also consider stakeholder interest for making long term profit (Freeman, Harrison, & Zyglidopoulos, 2018). A firm that has diverse board, focus on employee, customer and social responsibility make outstanding reputation in the market and its profit and sustainable growth also increases (Jones, Harrison, & Felps, 2018). Studies revealed that the financial performance of firms increases when they focus on robust stakeholder governance, which means firms manage organization affairs honestly and consider shareholders and stakeholder interests and take valuable risk management measures. As a result, stakeholders' interest and their EPS, ROE and Tobin's Q increases (Harrison & Wicks, 2013). Furthermore, a company operates efficiently when the strategic decisions are made

by diverse board members and independent directors (Post, Rahman, & Rubow, 2011). This study shows that FFP that is measured by Tobin's Q, ROA & EPS proxies increases when different factors like role of women on board, CEO duality, insider Shareholding, board independence contributes to corporate governance mechanism.

PROPOSITIONS

Board size

In CG the board size plays an essential role, large or small board may influence FFP via supervision competence and decision making for sustainability of the firm (Fama & Jensen, 1983). It has been noticed that large boards mean a board consisting of many members may influence FFP because it offers multiple skills and expertise that is beneficial for a firm to oversight the company's affairs effectively and due to this agency cost also reduces (Anderson et al., 2004; Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978; Westphal & Zajac, 1995).

Furthermore, a well-organized large board that manages the firm's matters efficiently may accelerate FFP through attracting investors, availing of good opportunities, creating great reputation in the market and developing tactical network (Vafeas, 2003). Nonetheless, there are the flaws of large board that may lead to probable governance issues like complications in boards members' communication and synchronization that may slow down strategic decision making (Jensen, 1993; Yermack, 1996).

Conflicting findings have been revealed by studies emphasizing large boards influence FFP positively (Eisenberg et al., 1998; Mak & Kusnadi, 2005; Jackling & Johl, 2009), while others claimed that large boards slow down strategic decision making that negatively influence FFP (Naushad & Malik, 2015; Al- Matari et al., 2012). P1: A favorable correlation exists between board size and firm's financial performance.

CEO duality

In CG, CEO duality persists controversy topic with assertion that often people declare CD increase FFP while some mentions duality of CEO means appointing a person as a CEO and chairperson is not an effective decision because giving too much power to a person may not be worthy and can be adverse for company. . It has been claimed by the advocates of CEO-chairman dual role that consolidating of dual leadership is beneficial for company as the priorities of executives and investors aligns, Dual role CEO has more power, so effective strategic decision making is implemented and company operations are managed effectively (Donaldson & Davis, 1991; Gill & Mathur, 2011). The stewardship theory recommends that dual role CEO has more authority that promotes dominant leadership and sustained stability, exclusively it has been seen in family-owned businesses where family has more control over the affairs of company (Ararat et al., 2017; Maury, 2006). It has been notified that the system to oversight the business affairs and board independence scale down because CEO duality directs to excessive power accumulation that often creates problems decision making (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Lorsch & MacIver, 1989). Empirical studies revealed that the company's financial outcomes where the leadership structures separate CEO and chairperson are good because transparency increases due to separate roles and managers are not holding excessive power (Rechner & Dalton, 1991; Balatbat et al., 2004).

Moreover, CD may influence firm performance negatively considering that he is not accountable to anyone and may prioritize his own interests (Firstenberg & Malkiel, 1994; Kyereboah-Coleman & Biekpe, 2006). CG discourage CD because the excession of power concentration to one person is not considered good for company despite this many businesses are family owned in Pakistan where the CD is commonly practiced (Yasser & Mamun, 2015). The contradictory approach emphasizes people have different opinions about CD some considered it good for company performance while the other considered it negatively. These different viewpoints tell that every company requires different governance mechanisms so every firm should make governance rules according to its need to oversight the managers effectively.

P2: A strong positive association is observed between CEO duality and firm's financial performance.

Board of independence

In CG, board independence plays a significant role with diverse approach from agency that say board should be more independent for effective management of directors while stewardship theory suggests that directors work for shareholders concerns. So, more independence of board is not essential. It has been proposed by agency theory that independent directors boost FFP through effective oversight on company's affairs and keep a proper check and balance on directors, so the risk of financial fraud reduces, and transparent decision-making is being ensured (Christensen et al., 2010; Fama & Jensen, 1983; Beasley, 1996).

Studies revealed that the firms having more non-executive directors that are actively engaged in firm's daily operations share additional details enhanced investors' reliance on company and FFP performance improved (Rosenstein & Wyatt, 1990; Yekini et al., 2015). Findings from Donaldson and Davis (1991) and Nicholson and Kiel (2007) indicate that insider directors have deeper knowledge of company so they have more ability to manage the company resource appropriately. The research finding board independence and firm performance has not given a specific result, due to independence of board shareholders trust increases on company (Jackling & Johl, 2009; Muniandy & Hillier, 2015; Yousaf et al., 2021), while the result of independence of board is increase in agency cost like decision making

becomes slow that could contribute to the firm's outcomes negatively (Agrawal et al., 2006; Christensen et al., 2010). There should be one third independent members on the corporate board as per regulations of corporate governance in Pakistan, the independent members means that members should not be linked with owner or the insiders so that effective decision making should be made. While in Pakistan, there are many family businesses which are managed by the members of the family, who have more control, so the influence of independent members is less as compared to family members (Naz et al., 2022; Tariq & Abbas, 2013). These divergent perspectives recommend that influence on FFP relies on market forces and corporate governance mechanism means if governance structure is good and market is stable then the impact of independent directors is good but if the market dynamics are not stable and governance system is not effective then this impact can be less or even negative.

P3: A constructive relationship is found between board independence and firm's financial performance.

Role of Women on Boards

It is a key component of CG that FFP significantly increases by having women on board. When there are males and females in the boardroom of company, they give their opinions according to their own perspectives, new ideas are generated, and proper assessment of risk or loss can be made (Adams & Ferreira, 2009). Women directors made good engagements with stakeholders, create value for company, do their job honestly and properly oversight the affairs of the company and promote effective CG. By this they obtained the trust of the investors and company gets benefits in the long run (Terjesen, Sealy, & Singh, 2009). It has been suggested by research that the inclusion of women in the boardroom is advantageous for the firm, their presence increases FFP because their monitoring mechanism is effective, corporate social responsibility is improved and agency cost also reduced (Post & Byron, 2015)). Notably, due to the involvement of women in the boardroom dishonesty and frauds also reduces, transparency and market trust increases (Gul, Srinidhi, & Ng, 2011). Moreover, it has been seen that the style of women leadership is unique as they accentuate collaboration and sustainability for company's long run efficient performance, they adopt effective strategies for risk management and decision making (Liu, Wei, & Xie, 2014). Though, the results of women on board of company are good but sometimes they are included in the board of company just to fulfill the legal requirements that is called tokenism due to this their ability to persuasion of the company's decision making also effects (Kramer, Konrad, & Erkut, 2006). Despite that, the companies that advocate gender diversity make higher profit by effective and fair management system and boost corporate sustainable growth and accountability Consequently, expansion of women's participation in board leadership has been observed generally good because they bring effective management and innovation that is essential for improved FFP and eventually they acquired the trust of stakeholders.

P4: There is a beneficial connection between role of women on board and firm's financial performance.

Insider shareholding

Insider shareholders mean the directors or executives of the corporate who holds corporation's share (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). It has been identified by Jensen and Meckling (1976), if the directors or executives own more shares of the corporation it generally affects the FFP and minimizes the agency cost. The explanation for this is that the managers or executives hold more shares of the firm so they will not pursue investing in high risky projects.

Consequently, managers will make investment in those projects where the chance of profit is comparatively higher than risk. While different investigations have shown increase in IS results in decrease in FFP. It is the opinion of Fama and Jensen (1983) that when directors or executives own more shares of the firm, they hold more corporate power ultimately it gets progressively tougher to control or eliminate them. A comprehensive analysis has been done by Gupta and Sachdeva (2017) to explore the impact of less and more IS on FFP. While certain investigations revealed that the firm's revenue increases when the IS increases about 20%. Conversely McConnell and Servaes (1990) have explored the firm's performance increases with rise in IS but when it rises about 40%_50% it negatively influences FFP. Nevertheless, it has been declared by Agrawal and Knoeber (1996) that

the impact of IS on firm's financial performance vanishes when the other mechanisms of corporate governance are included because they are also affecting firm's performance.

P5: A beneficial correlation exists between insider shareholder and firm's financial performance.

Audit committee

The responsibility of the audit committee is to check the monetary records of the firm to confirm that corporation has done its financial reporting according to the standards of CG. AC confirms that company has been disclosing the necessary information when required (Davidson et al., 2005). Findings from Kent and Stewart (2008) indicate that a company discloses more information whose board members and auditors have many meetings. Nevertheless, the opinion of the other scholars is different from this. It has been notified by Klein (1998) that no significant effect will be on FFP with the presence or absence of AC. Vafeas and Theodorou (1998) identifies that FFP is not specifically affected by CGM.

P6: There is a beneficial connection between audit committees and firm's financial performance.

Board diligence

Board diligence indicates that board members are dedicated with their duties they actively participate in firm matters like they attend the meeting, give their opinions in decision making management and oversight the affairs of the firms effectively. It has been noticed that a diligent board boosts the CG by effectively monitoring the company matters, solving the conflicts among shareholders and minimizing the agency cost. It also ensures that the rules and regulations are being followed appropriately (Halder & Nageswara Rao, 2021). Agency theory argues that when board members do work with dedication, fulfills all the responsibilities like oversight the company's matters, resolve firm's

conflicts then ultimately the FFP increases (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Studies revealed that the FFP enhances when members of the board are regularly participating in the meetings of board. As a result, accountability of the board strengthening means they know their responsibilities and fulfill them honestly and with devotion, risk management improves and financial irregularities also decreases (Brick & Chidambaran, 2010). It has been proved by data driven analysis, firms having diligent board members

influence firm's financial performance positively that may be measured by different proxies like Tobin's Q ROA and EPS (Palaniappan, 2017). Furthermore, board diligence plays an essential role in effective decision making for firm's long-term development and improves the standard of CG.

P7: A positive linkage exists between board diligence and firm's financial performance.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

DISCUSSION

This conceptual paper is based on the previous studies instead of data driven analysis. The framework consists of specific CG factors such as BS, CD, IS, BI, AC, RWB and BD that may influence FFP that can be measured by different proxies like Tobin's Q, ROA & EPS. In previous studies, the consequences of CG opting for diverse factors were tested on FFP, but RWB and BD were not included in the CGM. Prior explorations mainly included stewardship theory as well as agency theory. Nevertheless, this evaluation broadens the theoretical model by also involving stakeholder theory to provide more extensive viewpoint. Kyere and Ausloos (2021) recommend exploring stakeholder theory to explore new variables such as board diligence. Shakri et al. (2024) recommends exploring the role of women on board to provide new perspective and expansion of agency theory to fulfill the research gap. This theoretical framework can be empirically tested by future researchers. This theoretical framework reveals a strong linkage between the parameters of CG and FFP.

CONCLUSION:

The primary intent of this research was to develop a model for exploring the association between CG and FFP. The findings of this study show the factor like BS, CD, IS, BI, AC, RWB and BD may directly dominate the FFP. If these factors are not managed appropriately, then some factors such as firm size, leverage and industry as controllable variables. Finally, I developed this theoretical model to evaluate the role of CG in shaping FFP.

The beneficiaries of my research may be the researchers, investors, auditors, managers, auditors, and regulatory authorities who must make effective strategic decisions. Furthermore, the beneficiaries of my research can be the people who want to understand and explore the relationship between CG and FFP. The greatest limitation of this study is no practical data is collected to test this framework. Future research could empirically test this model by collecting practical data. However, they can incorporate other theories like resources independence theory and could explore factors like technology because they may influence up-to somehow FFP.

Declarations

Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate

This article is a conceptual study and does not involve human participants, animals, or primary data collection. Therefore, ethical approval and consent to participate are not applicable.

Consent for Publication

Not applicable.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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